

Analysis of WEDM Using ANSYS and FEM

Dheeraj Shukla*, Ashutosh Dwivedi
Student, Professor(H.O.D.)

Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Vindhya Institute of Technology and Science, Satna

Abstract:- Wire electrical discharge machining (WEDM) is widely used in machining of conductive materials when precision is considered as a prime importance. This work proposes a three dimensional finite element model (using ANSYS software) and new approach to predict the temperature distribution at different pulse time as well as stress distribution in wire. A transient thermal analysis assuming a Gaussian distribution heat source with temperature-dependent material properties has been used to investigate the temperature distribution and stress distribution. Thermal stress developed after the end of the spark and residual stress developed after subsequent cooling. The effect on significant machining parameter pulse-on-time has been investigated and found that the peak temperature sharply increases with the parameter.

Keywords: ANSYS, WEDM, Residual Stress, Thermal Stress, Temperature.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wire electrical discharge machining process is a mostly used non-conventional material removal processes. This is use for manufacturing difficult shape and profile of hard materials. This is considering as a distinctive variation of the conventional electrical discharge machining processes. In the WEDM, demand is growing for high rate cutting speed and high accuracy machining for improve the productivity of product and also for achieve high excellence quality in machining job. In wire electrical discharge machining process a always travelling wire electrode made of thin copper, brass or tungsten of diameter 0.05–0.3 mm is used, which is precisely controlled by a CNC system. Here role of CNC is very important. The function of CNC is unwind the wire from a first spool, and feed throughout the work-piece, and takes it on a second spool. Generally wire velocity varies from 0.1 to 10 m/min, and feed rate is 2 to 6 mm/min. A direct current is used for generate high frequency pulse to the wire and the workpiece. The wire (electrode) is hold in tensioning device for decreases the chance of producing inaccurate parts. In wire electrical machining process, the workpiece and tool is eroded and there is no direct contact between the workpiece and the electrode, and this reduces the stress during machining.

WEDM was initially developed by manufacturing industry in the since 1960. The development technique is replaced the machined electrode used in electrical discharge machining. In 1974, D.H. Dulebohn introduced the optical line follower system which is automatic control the shapes

of the part to be machined by the wire electrical discharge machining process. In 1975, it was popular rapidly, and its capability was better understood by manufacturing industry. When the computer numerical control system was introduced in WEDM process this brought about a most important development of the machining proce.

Consequently the wide capability of the wire electrical discharge machining process was widely exploited for any through-hole machining owing to the wire, which has to pass through the part to be machined. The common application of wire electrical discharge machining process is the fabricate the stamp and extrusion tools and dies, fixtures and gauges, prototypes, aircraft and medical parts, and grinding wheel form tools.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the wire EDM, a series of rapid electric spark occur in the gap between tool (wire) and workpiece. Addition of particles into the dielectric fluid makes this process more complex and random. The following assumptions are made without sacrificing the basic features of the wire EDM model to make the problem mathematically feasible.

A. Thermal Model of Wire EDM

The working principal of WEDM is as same EDM process, when the distance between the two electrodes (wire and the workpiece) is reduced the intensity of electric field in the volume between the electrodes (wire and the workpiece), become greater than the strength of the dielectric, which breaks, allowing current to flow between the two electrodes. For this reason the spark will generated.

B. Finite Element Analysis Procedure Using ANSYS Software

➤ Thermal Analysis of Brass Wire

The general finite element modeling procedure consists of the following steps:

- Preferences
- ✓ Thermal
- Preprocessing
- ✓ Definition of Element Type
- ✓ Material Properties Definition
- ✓ Model Generation
- ✓ Meshing

- Solution
- ✓ Defining Initial Condition
- ✓ Applying Boundary Condition
- ✓ Applying Load
- ✓ Solving For Results

- Post Processing
- ✓ Reading Result File
- ✓ Viewing Results

- Process of Thermo-Structural Modeling
- Open Mechanical Apdl (Ansys).
- Go To File > Change Title And Give A New Title For The Example.
- Preferences
- Preprocessing>Element Type> Add/Edit/Delete

- ✓ Click on Add
- ✓ Select Thermal Solid on the Left List and Brick 8 Node 70 on Right List(I.E. Element Type) Click on Ok
- ✓ Close
- ✓ Material Properties>Temperature Unit>Celsius>Ok
- ✓ Material Models>Thermal >Conductivity>Isotropic>Ok ,Put Value>Density Put Value>Specific Heat Put Value>Material Exit
- ✓ Modeling>Create>Cylinder>Solid Cylinder>Put the Dimensions
- ✓ Meshing>Mesh Tool> Smart Size 6>Mesh >Ok

- ✓ Thermal>Heat Flux>On Element>Select Proper Element>Ok
- ✓ Initial Condition>Define>Pick All>Temperature>21⁰C
- ✓ Solve >Current LS

- Post Processing>Plot Results>Counter Plot>Nodal Solution>DOF Solution>Nodal Temperature>OK
- ✓ Finish
- ✓ Physics> Environment>Read >Structural>Ok
- ✓ Solution Control>Putting The T_{on} Time> Automatic Time Stepping ON>No. Of Subsets
- ✓ Apply>Structural>Displacement>Area>All DOF>OK
- ✓ Solution Load Step>Write LS File>1>Ok
- ✓ Analysis Type>Solution Control>Basic>Off Time>Transient>Ramped Loading
- ✓ Defineload>Apply>Temperature>From Thermal Analysis>Browse>File.Rth>Ok

Post processing>plot results>counter plot>nodal solution>DOF solution>nodal temperature>OK

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. ANSYS Model Confirmation

In this section we have firstly make a model of WEDM process for brass wire with parameter setting as given in Table 3. Later the value has been compared with Han et al. Fig. 6 shows temperature distribution in brass wire, which is approximately same of Han et al. model. So we can say that we are proceeding in right way. Thermal modeling has done in using ANSYS.

B. FEM Analysis

➤ Thermal Modeling of Wire EDM for Single Spark in Brass Wire

Main parameters of the thermal analysis (analysis parameters)

Table 1 Parameters Used for Thermal Analysis in WEDM Process

Parameter	Unit	Value
Peak current of electro-discharge	A	27
Voltage of electro discharge,	V	25
Duration of single pulse	μs	0.12, 0.26, 0.36, 0.52, 0.58,
Wire radius	Mm	1.2, 1.82
Convective coefficient	W/m ² °C	0.05
Temperature of the dielectric Poisson' ratio	0 _C	3040
Coefficient of linear thermal expansion	K ⁻¹	21

Fig 1 Three-Dimensional View of the Meshed Model

- ✓ Physics> Environment>Write >Physics File Title>Thermal>Ok
- ✓ Element Type>Switch Element Type>Change>Element Type>Thermal To Structural>Ok
- ✓ Material Properties>Structural>Linear>Isotropic>Thermal Expansion>Ok>Exit
- ✓ Physics> Environment>Write >Erase Thermal>Write Structural>Ok
- ✓ Solution>New Analysis Type>Transient>Full>Ok
- ✓ Solution Control>Putting The T_{on} Time> Automatic Time Stepping ON>No. Of Subsets
- ✓ Define Loads>Apply>Functions>Read File>Ok

Fig 2 Temperature Distribution In Brass Wire With $V=25V$, $I=27 A$, $P=0.38$ And $T_{on}=0.12\mu s$

Fig 5 Temperature Distribution In Brass Wire With $V=25V$, $I=27 A$, $P=0.38$ And $T_{on}=0.52\mu s$

Fig 3 Temperature Distribution In Brass Wire With $V=25V$, $I=27 A$, $P=0.38$ And $T_{on}=0.26\mu s$

Fig 6 Temperature Distribution In Brass Wire With $V=25V$, $I=27 A$, $P=0.38$ And $T_{on}=0.58\mu s$

Fig 4 Temperature Distribution In Brass Wire With $V=25V$, $I=27 A$, $P=0.38$ And $T_{on}=0.36\mu s$

Fig 7 Temperature Distribution In Brass Wire With $V=25V$, $I=27 A$, $P=0.38$ And $T_{on}=1.2\mu s$

Fig 8 Temperature Distribution In Brass Wire With $V=25V$, $I=27 A$, $P=0.38$ And $T_{on}= 1.82\mu s$

Fig 10 Graph of Displacement

➤ *Structural Modeling of WEDM in Molybdenum Wire*

In this section we have firstly make a model of WEDM process for brass wire with parameter setting as given in Table 4. Later the value has been compared with Saha et al. Fig. 6 shows displacement molybdenum wire, which is approximately same of Saha et al. So we can say that we are proceeding in right way. The structural analysis has done of molybdenum wire.

• *Displacement Analysis in the Wire Due to Tension:*

After solving for the temperature distribution we attempt to find the displacement in the wire. Now in this case molybdenum wire is used. Process parameters used for analysis is shown below Table 2

Table 2 Parameters used for structural analysis in WEDM process

Parameter	Units	Value
Radius of wire	Mm	0.125
Length of wire	M	
Tension	N	0.1
Initial temperature	K	
Working	K	13.7295

• The displacement graph is shown in below:

Fig 9 Nodal Solution of Displacement

- *Thermo-Structural Analysis of WEDM in Brass Wire.*
- *Thermal Stress Modelling of Micro Wire EDM for Single Discharge*

Fig 11 Thermal Stress in X-Component at $T_{on}=0.12\mu s$

Fig 12 Thermal Stress in Y-Component at $T_{on}=0.12\mu s$

Fig 13 Thermal Stress in Z-Component at $T_{on}=0.12\mu s$

Fig 16 Thermal Shear Stress in YZ-Component at $T_{on}=0.12\mu s$

Fig 14 Thermal Shear Stress in XY Component at $T_{on}=0.12\mu s$

Fig 17 Residual Stress at $T_{off} = 3\mu s$

Fig 15 Thermal shear stress in XZ component at $t_{on}=0.12\mu s$

Fig 18 Thermal Stress in X-Component at $T_{on}=0.52\mu s$

Fig 19 Thermal Stress in Y-component at $t_{on}=0.52\mu s$

Fig 22 Thermal Shear Stress in YZ-Component at $T_{on}=0.52\mu s$

Fig 20 Thermal Stress in Z-Component at $T_{on}=0.52\mu s$

Fig 23 Residual Stress at $t_{off}= 3\mu s$

Fig 21 Thermal Shear Stress in XY-Component at $T_{on}=0.52\mu s$

Fig 24 Thermal Stress in X-Component at $T_{on}=1.82\mu s$

Fig 25 Thermal Stress in Y-Component at $t_{on}=1.82\mu s$

Fig 28 Thermal Stress in XZ-Component at $t_{on}=1.82\mu s$

Fig 26 Thermal Stress in Z-Component at $T_{on}=1.82\mu s$

Fig 29 Thermal Stress in YZ-Component at $t_{on}=1.82\mu s$

Fig 27 Thermal Stress in XY-Component at $T_{on}=1.82\mu s$

Fig 30 Residual Stress at $T_{off}= 3 \mu s$ 2.5 Results and Discussions

Temperature distributions at the end of the pulse time are shown in Figs.(3- 9) to know the effects on WEDM. The

temperature distribution during single discharge is calculated with the energy input constant parameter $I_p=27$ A, voltage $=25V$ with varying pulse time. At pulse time = $0.12 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $86.75^\circ C$. At pulse time = $0.26 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $247.7^\circ C$. At pulse time = $0.36 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $318.6^\circ C$. At pulse time = $0.52 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $446.9^\circ C$. At pulse time = $0.58 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $578.335^\circ C$. At pulse time = $1.2 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $854.8^\circ C$. At pulse time = $1.82 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $1144^\circ C$. Further increasing the pulse time is not possible because, at temperature $1083^\circ C$, the brass wire melt.

The distinctive stress distributions in WEDM process, enumerated at the end of heating cycle are presented. Here, Gaussian heat flux distribution is used for the calculation of temperature distribution. Later on, by varying the parameter i.e. pulse duration, and study of thermal stresses are presented. Fig 10-34 shows the thermal stress in different pulse on time. Thermal stress developed after the end of the spark and residual stress developed after subsequent cooling. The nature of the maximum stress is compressive, and it is because during the pulse duration, the heat flux supplied to the tool electrode for a very short duration (in μs). The maximum compressive stress is $563 MPa$ for $t_{on}=0.12 \mu s$ in X-component, and maximum residual stress is $778 MPa$. The maximum compressive stress is $288 MPa$ for $t_{on}=0.52 \mu s$ in Z-component and maximum residual stress is $288 MPa$. The maximum compressive stress is $425 MPa$ for $t_{on}=1.82 \mu s$ in Z-component and maximum residual stress is $533 MPa$.

IV. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this dissertation, a robust three dimensional finite element model has been developed using ANSYS software to predict the temperature distribution at different pulse time as well as stress distribution in the wire of WEDM. A transient thermal analysis assuming a Gaussian distribution heat source with temperature-dependent material properties has been used to investigate the temperature distribution and stress distribution. Thermal stress was developed after the end of the spark and also residual stress was developed after subsequent cooling. Finite element modeling was carried out for a single spark with temperature-dependent material properties. Certain parameters such as spark radius, discharge current and discharge duration, the latent heat, the plasma channel radius and Gaussian distribution of heat flux, the percentage of discharge energy transferred to the tool electrode have made this study nearer to real process conditions. The FE model shows that, at pulse time = $0.12 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $86.75^\circ C$ and maximum residual stress is $778 MPa$. At pulse time = $0.26 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $247.7^\circ C$ and .At pulse time = $0.36 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $318.6^\circ C$. At pulse time = $0.52 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $446.9^\circ C$ and the maximum compressive stress is $288 MPa$ in Z-component, and maximum residual stress is $288 MPa$. . At pulse time = $0.58 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is

$578.335^\circ C$. At pulse time = $1.2 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $854.8^\circ C$. At pulse time = $1.82 \mu s$, corresponding temperature is $1144^\circ C$ and the maximum compressive stress is $425 MPa$ for $t_{on}=1.82 \mu s$ in Z-component, and maximum residual stress is $533 MPa$.

Further increasing the pulse time is not possible because, at temperature $1083^\circ C$, the brass wire melt.

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